

DETERMINATION OF DIAGNOSTIC PARAMETERS OF ELECTRIC AND ELECTRONIC EQUIPMENT OF AUTOMOBILES

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Abstract: This article describes the use of electrical and electronic equipment of passenger cars, diagnostics of electrical and electronic equipment, and its advantages and disadvantages. Basics of diagnostic methods for breakdown of electrical and electronic equipment are provided for each device, diagnostic problems and ways to solve them are highlighted.

Key words: automobile, electrical and electronic equipment, diagnostic parameters, generator and voltage regulators, relay regulator, starter, ignition system, spark plug.

Unbroken operation of electrical and electronic equipment of cars and increases operational reliability of the entire car model. The reason for this is that there are many parts of the car that are directly connected to electricity. Diagnostics of electrical and electronic components is an important and constantly performed type of work in technical service. Diagnostic parameters are used to assess the technical condition of vehicles due to the limited possibility of direct measurement of structural parameters. They allow to determine the technical condition of the object and are characterized by more convenient measurements. Diagnostic parameters are an indirect view of the breakdown (faults). The value of the diagnostic parameter can be determined without dividing the object into pieces.

A diagnostic parameter is a qualitative measure that determines the quantitative value of the technical condition of the vehicle, its aggregates and nodes

without dividing it into parts by indirect signs (symptoms). Diagnostic parameters are connected with structural parameters and provide necessary information about the technical condition of the object.

Assessing the technical condition of the object using diagnostic parameters allows reducing the amount of diagnostic work and increasing its speed. With the help of diagnostic parameters, it is possible to assess the technical condition of non-compartmentalized elements and complex systems. But to measure diagnostic parameters, complex and expensive equipment is needed, which puts high demands on employees.

The theory and practice of vehicle technical diagnostics is based on the dependence of the parameters of output characteristics on the structural parameters of the object.

Active or concurrent (companion) output processes are considered as an indirect external sign (symptom) indicating a faulty technical condition of the object. [3].

Diagnostic parameters of electrical and electronic equipment of cars.

Diagnostic parameters of generators and voltage regulators

Figure 1. Lassetti car generator WAI 114350

Figure 2. Voltage regulator 93740783-MUNHWA(KOREA) brand for Lassetti cars

In modern cars, relay-regulators have greatly simplified the application, maintenance and repair of shared alternators. The main malfunctions of the generator are wear of contact rings and brushes, various breakdowns and malfunctions of brushes, disconnection of starter and rotor wires, intermediate short circuit of stator wires and their short circuit with the body, rectifier block and diodes breakage or

failure, loosening, excessive tension or wear of the belt, etc. The main fault of the regulator (relay-regulator) is the deviation of the regulation voltage from the norm, which is usually 13.7-4.2V for 12 V devices. The generator unit is diagnosed on the voltmeter memory. In this case, in addition to the limiting voltage, it is possible to check the performance of the generator. When checking the limiting voltage, current consumers are triggered, the frequency of rotations of the crankshaft increases. The performance of the generator is assessed by the voltage when it gives all its power to the frequency of rotations and when current consumers (melting devices) are connected. The voltage should not be less than 12V. However, even if there is an additional test mode, such a test method cannot detect faults such as disconnection of the alternating current generator or short circuit of the stator windings with the body, or breakdown and failure of the rectifier diodes, which take into account the reserve of the generator's ability to work in many ways. The specified faults are easily detected by the oscillogram, but for this, special measuring channels are required, which are mainly provided in expensive equipment. A faulty generator must be replaced for electrical workshop repair. The limiting voltage for contact relay-regulators is adjusted by tensioning the armature spring. When the limiting voltage of the regulators together with the generator does not match, it must be replaced.

Diagnostic parameters of the starter. In the process of operation, mechanical damage occurs in the starter, mainly due to the reduction of free-running coupling, gear wear or compression. These faults can be eliminated by replacing the switch. Malfunctions of the starter electrical circuit due to oxidation of contacts and relay contacts working under lower power, disconnection of wires. In this case, the performance of the starter will deteriorate, it will be necessary to disassemble and disassemble it. In a special device, the torque produced by the removed starter, the current consumption in the working mode and in the full braking mode, and the frequency of rotation of the armature in the working mode are checked. It is also possible to check the current in full braking mode without removing the starter from

the car. Consumption is often done, that is, the current increases when the starter circuit is short-circuited, and decreases when the contacts, brush and collector are oxidized. However, this method is not often used in practice due to its complexity.

Figure 3. Stater of the Lassetti car

Diagnostic parameter of the ignition system. Troubleshooting of electrical equipment during the use of cars makes up 11...17% of TS and JT work volumes, and according to statistics, about 40% of failures and breakdowns in carburetor engines are related to the ignition system will come. These, in turn, often lead to an increase in fuel consumption by 5...6%.

We will consider the occurrence of failures in the elements of the ignition system separately for each of them. High voltage coil failures include cracking and burning of the coil cover, disconnection of the primary and secondary windings, disconnection of the auxiliary resistor, or loose connections. Currently produced 12V35AH and 12V55AH (MF) accumulator batteries have special indicators that show the battery is normal (green color), charge requirement (black color) and low electrolyte (colorless). Depending on the color of the indicator, it is possible to determine the need to charge the battery.

Figure 4. Ignition system

Battery, contact-transistor, non-contact-transistor and electronic ignition systems are used in cars. More than 40% of engine failures occur in this system, causing its power to decrease. The most common ignition system is battery-powered, which consists of a switch-connector, an ignition coil, a spark plug, and high and low voltage wires.

The most common malfunctions of the ignition system are high and low voltage wires exposed to the top cover and touching the ground, lack of good contact at the connection points, oxidation and burning of the switch-connector contacts, changes in the gap between the contacts, moving contact loose spring, worn distributor shaft, breakdown and failure of the condenser, oil splatter on the spark plugs, short circuit of the ignition coil wires, incorrect setting of the ignition torque, from the center is that the escapement and vacuum ignition adjusters do not work well.

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